

EFFECT OF STRESS RATIO ON FATIGUE CHARACTERISTICS IN THE OUT-OF-PLANE DIRECTION OF THICK CFRP LAMINATES WITH TOUGHENED INTERLAMINAR LAYERS

Atsushi Hosoi¹, Shigeyoshi Sakuma², Sen Seki², Yuzo Fujita³, Ichiro Taketa³ and Hiroyuki Kawada¹

¹Department of Applied Mechanics and Aerospace Engineering, Waseda University
3-4-1 Okubo, Shinjuku-ku, Tokyo 169-8555, Japan
Email: hos@aoni.waseda.jp, web page: <http://www.waseda.jp/top/en>

²Graduate School of Fundamental Science and Engineering, Waseda University
3-4-1 Okubo, Shinjuku-ku, Tokyo 169-8555, Japan

³Composite Materials Research Laboratories, Toray Industries, Inc.
1515, Tsutsui Masaki-cho, Iyogun, Ehime 791-3193, Japan

Keywords: Fatigue, out-of-plane, stress ratio, toughened interlaminar layers, thick CFRP laminates

ABSTRACT

The effect of the stress ratio on fatigue characteristics in the out-of-plane direction of thick carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) laminates with toughened interlaminar layers was evaluated. The spool shaped specimens cut out the unidirectional thick CFRP laminates, which pile up 88 plies of the prepreg with toughened interlaminar layer, T800S/3900-2B, were used. The fatigue tests were conducted under the stress ratios of $R = 0.1$ and -1 to evaluate the effect of the stress ratio. As the results of the fatigue tests, the fatigue life of the specimens at $R = -1$ was shorter than that at $R = 0.1$. It was found that the fatigue properties of the CFRP laminates in the out-of-plane direction are affected by the stress amplitude from the experimental results. In addition, the fatigue life under the different stress ratio can be evaluated equivalently using the Walker model which can consider the mean stress effect.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) laminates with toughened interlaminar layers have been developed to improve the compression after impact (CAI) strength [1]. The CFRP laminates with toughened interlaminar layers have approximately double CAI strength of the conventional ones without toughened interlaminar layers and they are used as the main structural members of the latest airplane. However, it has been pointed out that it is important to evaluate precisely the mechanical properties of the thick CFRP laminates with toughened interlaminar layers in the out-of-plane direction. Kashiwagi et al. [2] conducted the static bending tests using the CFRP L-shaped curved beam samples, which imitate a main wing spar of an airplane, formed of the prepreg with toughened interlaminar layer, T800S/3900-2B. They showed that the Mode I delamination crack propagated from an inserted film in the width direction at the curved part and they concluded that the depression effect of delamination propagation assumed from the tests with coupon specimens could not be obtained because the delamination crack propagated in not toughened interlaminar layer but fiber layer. Authors [3] conducted the static tensile tests and tensile fatigue tests of thick CFRP laminates with toughened interlaminar layers in the out-of-plane direction. We showed that the fracture occurred mainly in a fiber layer under both static and fatigue tests and the fatigue strength in the out-of-plane direction was lower than that in the in-plane transverse direction of the coupon specimens.

Some studies about the mechanical properties in the out-of-plane direction of the thick CFRP laminates have evaluated mainly under static tensile loading [4]. On the other hand, the effects of the compressive stress and the stress ratio on the fatigue properties have not been cleared. Therefore, the effect of the stress ratio on the fatigue properties in the out-of-plane direction of the thick CFRP laminates with toughened interlaminar layers was evaluated in this study.

2 EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Specimen

The unidirectional thick CFRP laminates, which pile up 88 layers of the prepreg with toughened interlaminar layer, T800S/3900-2B, were formed with an autoclave. The fiber volume fraction of the laminates is $V_f = 56\%$, and the cure temperature is 453 K. For evaluating the tensile strength of the CFRP laminates in the out-of-plane direction, Hara et al. [4] proposed to use a spool specimen rather than a cylindrical specimen and choose a thick specimen with a large waist radius. Thus, the specimen dimensions as shown in Fig. 1 were decided in reference to the study by them. The specimens were machined from the approximately 17 mm thick laminates. The shape of specimens is a cylinder solid with a narrow part like a spool shape. The diameters of the minimum and maximum cross-section surfaces are 18.75 mm and 25.0 mm, respectively. The roughness on the specimen surface was less than $Ra = 0.4 \mu\text{m}$. Metal tabs were bonded to the upper and lower surfaces of the specimen.

Figure 1: Specimen geometry.

2.2 Test conditions

Static tensile tests and fatigue tests were conducted with a hydraulic testing machine. The shaft centering device was used to attach the specimen to the testing machine. The static tensile tests were performed under displacement control at a crosshead speed of 0.1 mm/min. Four strain gages were stuck on the surface of the minimum cross section of the specimen. Fatigue tests were run at a frequency of $f = 5$ Hz and a stress ratio of $R = 0.1$ or -1 under load control. The stress level was set at $\sigma_{\max}/\sigma_b = 0.5-0.75$. The fatigue tests were interrupted when the specimen did not fracture up to 10^6 cycles. The fracture surface of the specimens was observed with optical microscopy.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1 Evaluation of fatigue life

Figure 2 shows the S-N curve under the test conditions at the stress ratio of $R = 0.1$ and -1 . The vertical axis shows the average maximum stress at the minimum cross section. The fatigue life of the specimens at $R = -1$ is shorter than that at $R = 0.1$. It was cleared that the fatigue properties of the CFRP laminates in the out-of-plane direction is affected by the stress amplitude from the experimental results. It is thought that the difference of the fatigue life is caused by the plastic deformation of the matrix resin. The stress concentration occurs at matrix resin around carbon fibers under loadings and the local plastic deformation is caused around the carbon fibers even when the compressive stress is applied in the specimen [5]. Therefore, it is thought that micro damage accumulated per cycle under the fatigue test at $R = -1$ is greater than that at $R = 0.1$.

3.2 Damage observation

Figure 3 shows the fracture surface after the fatigue test at stress ratio of $R = -1$. It is found that the main fracture surface is fiber layer. It is thought that the fatigue crack propagated in the fiber layer because the fracture toughness of the fiber layer is lower than that of the toughened interlaminar layer. The similar fracture surface was observed for the specimens after static tensile tests and fatigue tests at stress ratio of $R = 0.1$. It was difficult to observe the initiation and propagation of a crack in this study. The stiffness reduction of the specimen was only a few percent until just before the fracture, and the stiffness reduced directly before the fracture. Therefore, it is thought that the critical crack length is very short and the crack propagated instantly and unstably in the specimen within the test conditions in this study.

Figure 2: S-N diagram of CFRP specimens.

Figure 3: Fracture surfaces of the specimen after fatigue test at stress ratio of $R = -1.0$.

4 STRESS ANALYSIS

Three-dimensional finite element (FE) analysis was carried out using the COMSOL program code. A one-eighth model was used for the analysis. The quadratic tetrahedron elements were used in the model. The minimum element size and the number of elements were 40 μm and 827168, respectively. The FE model is shown in Fig. 4. Each fiber layer and toughened interlaminar layer was modelled near the minimum cross section of the specimen and the other part was modelled as an orthotropic material. The thickness of the fiber layer and the toughened interlaminar layer was 165.4 μm and 22.6 μm from the observation of the specimen surface, respectively. The displacement in a direction perpendicular to loading direction was fixed on the top surface of the model to express the restriction by the tab. The force of 2.07 kN, which becomes the average out-of-plane normal stress of 30 MPa at the minimum cross section area, was applied on the top surface of the model. The model was calculated as the room temperature of 293 K.

Table 1 shows the mechanical properties of the unidirectional laminates formed of T800S/3900-2B prepreg. The longitudinal, transverse and out-of-plane elastic moduli and the in plane and out-of-plane Poisson's ratios were measured using the rectangular parallelepiped specimen cut out from the 17 mm thick unidirectional CFRP laminates by static compressive tests, respectively. The in-plane and out-of-plane shear moduli were measured using the V-notched specimen cut out from the thick CFRP laminates by four point bending tests on the basis of ASTM D 5379. Longitudinal and transverse thermal expansion coefficient were measured with thin unidirectional CFRP laminates using a thermal mechanical analyzer. Out-of-plane thermal expansion coefficient were evaluated by measuring the strain change of a cubic CFRP sample cut out from the thick CFRP laminates within the temperature range from 313 K to 453 K in a thermostat bath. The mechanical properties of the fiber layers and toughened interlaminar layers were calculated with a mixture law using the mechanical properties of the unidirectional laminates as follows. Fiber layers were assumed to be an orthotropic material that transverse and out-of-plane elastic moduli are equal, and toughened interlaminar layers were assumed to be an isotropic material.

$$E_L = E_L^f \rho_f + E_i \rho_i, E_T = E_T^f \rho_f + E_i \rho_i, E_Z = \frac{1}{\frac{\rho_f}{E_Z^f} + \frac{\rho_i}{E_i}} \quad (1)$$

$$\nu_{LZ} = \rho_f \nu_{LZ}^f + \rho_i \nu_i, \nu_{TZ} = \rho_f \nu_{TZ}^f + \rho_i \nu_i, \nu_{LT}^f = \nu_{LZ}^f, \ln \nu_i = V_p \ln \nu_p + V_e \ln \nu_e \quad (2)$$

$$G_{LZ} = \frac{1}{\frac{\rho_f}{G_{LZ}^f} + \frac{\rho_i}{G_i}}, G_{TZ} = \frac{1}{\frac{\rho_f}{G_{TZ}^f} + \frac{\rho_i}{G_i}}, G_{LT}^f = G_{LZ}^f, G_i = \frac{E_i}{2(1+\nu_i)} \quad (3)$$

$$\alpha_L = \frac{\alpha_L^f E_L^f \rho_f + \alpha_i E_i \rho_i}{E_L^f \rho_f + E_i \rho_i}, \alpha_T = \frac{\alpha_T^f E_T^f \rho_f + \alpha_i E_i \rho_i}{E_T^f \rho_f + E_i \rho_i}, \alpha_T^f = \alpha_Z^f \quad (4)$$

$$\alpha_Z = \alpha_Z^f \rho_f + \alpha_i \rho_i + \rho_f (\alpha_L^f - \alpha_L) \nu_{LZ}^f + \rho_f (\alpha_T^f - \alpha_T) \nu_{TZ}^f + \rho_i (2\alpha_i - \alpha_L - \alpha_T) \nu_i.$$

Where, superscript or subscript f and i indicate fiber layer and toughened interlaminar layer, respectively. ρ is the thickness ratio of fiber layer and toughened interlaminar layer. In this study, $\rho_f = 0.88$ and $\rho_i = 0.12$ were used. The Poisson's ratio of toughened interlaminar layer ν_i was calculated considering the volume fraction of polyamide and epoxy resins, V_p and V_e . The subscripts p and e show the polyamide and epoxy resins, respectively in Eq. (2). In this study, $V_p = 0.65$ and $V_e = 0.35$ were used from the observation of the specimen surface, and the Poisson's ratios of the polyamide and epoxy resins were used as $\nu_p = 0.45$ and $\nu_e = 0.42$.

Figures 5 and 6 shows the analytical results of out-of-plane normal stress, σ_z . Figure 5 shows the stress distribution and Fig. 6 shows the stress distribution of σ_z of thickness direction along the surface

of $\theta = 0^\circ$ direction. It is found that the stress singularity field occurred near the interface between the fiber and toughened interlaminar layers. The maximum stress of σ_z is applied on the surface of $\theta = 0^\circ$ direction in the first fiber layer from the central plane. The compressive stress is applied in the toughened interlaminar layers on the surface because of the free-edge effect.

Figure 4: One-eighth FE model of the specimen.

Table 1: Mechanical properties of unidirectional laminates.

Longitudinal elastic modulus	E_L	GPa	134
Transverse elastic modulus	E_T	GPa	8.62
Out-of-plane elastic modulus	E_Z	GPa	8.20
In-plane shear modulus	G_{LT}	GPa	4.68
Out-of-plane shear modulus in longitudinal direction	G_{LZ}	GPa	3.78
Out-of-plane shear modulus in transverse direction	G_{TZ}	GPa	2.38
In-plane Poisson's ratio	ν_{LT}		0.338
Out-of-plane Poisson's ratio in longitudinal direction	ν_{LZ}		0.318
Out-of-plane Poisson's ratio in transverse direction	ν_{TZ}		0.571
Longitudinal thermal expansion coefficient	α_L	$\times 10^{-6} / K$	0.188
Transverse thermal expansion coefficient	α_T	$\times 10^{-6} / K$	33.5
Out-of-plane thermal expansion coefficient	α_Z	$\times 10^{-6} / K$	44.3

Figure 5: Stress distribution of out-of-plane normal stress, σ_z .

Figure 6: Stress distribution of σ_z of thickness direction along the surface of $\theta = 0^\circ$ direction.

5 EVALUATION OF FATIGUE LIFE BY WALKER MODEL

Some methods have been proposed to evaluate the mean stress effect, such as the methods by Gerber [6], Goodman [7], Soderberg [8], Morrow [9], Smith-Watson-Topper (SWT) [10] and Walker [11]. In this study, the Walker model was used to evaluate the fatigue life as given by

$$\sigma_{ar} = \sigma_{max}^{1-\gamma} \sigma_a^\gamma = \sigma_{max} \left(\frac{1-R}{2} \right)^\gamma \quad (5)$$

where σ_{max} is the applied maximum stress, σ_a is the stress amplitude, σ_{ar} is the equivalent fully reversed stress amplitude and γ is a constant obtained from the experiments. The relationship between the fatigue life and the equivalent fully reversed stress amplitude based on Basquin's equation is given as

$$\sigma_{ar} = \sigma'_f (2N_f)^b \quad (6)$$

where σ'_f and b are the fatigue strength coefficient and exponent constant, respectively.

The fatigue crack propagated to the fiber layer of the specimen from the observation results. From the results calculated by the FE analysis, the maximum stress of σ_z is applied on the surface of $\theta = 0^\circ$ direction in the first fiber layer from the central plane. Therefore, the fatigue life of the specimen was evaluated with the average out-of-plane stress, $\sigma_{z, ave}$, on the surface of the first fiber layer in the z direction at $\theta = 0^\circ$. Figure 7 shows the S-N curve evaluated with equations (5) and (6). The constants are $\sigma'_f = 51.5$, $b = -6.77 \times 10^{-3}$ and $\gamma = 0.166$, respectively. It is found that the effect of stress ratio on the fatigue life can be evaluated equivalently with the Walker model. The usefulness of the Walker model has shown with many metallic materials [12]. It is expected that the effect of stress ratio on the fatigue properties in the out-of-plane direction of CFRP laminates can be evaluated appropriately and simply with the model by conducting the fatigue tests with the further test conditions.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The effect of the stress ratio on fatigue properties of thick CFRP laminates with toughened interlaminar layers was evaluated in this study. From the results of the fatigue tests, it was cleared that the fatigue life of the specimen at the stress ratio of $R = -1$ is shorter than that of $R = 0.1$ and the fatigue crack propagated in the fiber layer from the observation on the fracture surface. It was thought that the local plastic deformation in the matrix resin around carbon fibers causes the difference of the fatigue life. From the results of the FE analysis, it was found that the maximum stress of σ_z is applied on the surface of $\theta = 0^\circ$ direction in the first fiber layer from the central plane. The compressive stress is applied in the vicinity of the surface of the toughened interlaminar layers because of the free-edge effect.

Figure 7: S-N diagram of thick CFRP laminates evaluated by the Walker model.

Finally, it was shown that the fatigue life of the specimen at the different stress ratio of $R = 0.1$ and -1 can be evaluated equivalently using the Walker model.

REFERENCES

- [1] N. Odagiri, H. Kishi and M. Yamashita, Development of TORAYCA prepreg P2302 carbon fiber reinforced plastic for aircraft primary structural materials, *Advanced Composite Materials*, **5**, 1996, pp.249-252 (doi: 10.1163/156855196X00301).
- [2] M. Kashiwagi, Y. Nonaka, T. Abe and M. Yamashita, Interlaminar strength of CFRP curved beam with different toughened-material systems, *Transactions of the Japan Society of Mechanical Engineers Series A*, **78**, 2012, pp. 577-581 (doi: 10.1299/kikaia.78.577)
- [3] K. Shigemori, A. Hosoi, Y. Fujita and H. Kawada, Fatigue strength properties of interlaminar toughened CFRP laminates under cyclic loading in the out-of-plane direction, *Transactions of the Japan Society of Mechanical Engineers*, **80**, 2014, p. SMM0087 (doi: 10.1299/transjsme.2014smm0087)
- [4] E. Hara, T. Yokozeki, H. Hatta, T. Ishikawa and Y. Iwahori, Effects of geometry and specimen size on out-of-plane tensile strength of aligned CFRP determined by direct tensile method, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **41**, 2010, pp. 1425-1433 (doi: 10.1016/j.compositesa.2010.06.003).
- [5] K. Kurihara, A. Hosoi, N. Sato and H. Kawada, Effect of ply thickness on transverse crack initiation in CFRP cross-ply laminates under fatigue loading, *Transactions of the Japan Society of Mechanical Engineers Series A*, **79**, 2013, pp. 249-265 (doi: 10.1299/kikaia.79.249).
- [6] W. Gerber, Calculation of the allowable stresses in iron structures, *Zeitschrift des Bayerischen Architekten und Ingenieur-Vereins*, **6**, 1874, pp. 101-110.
- [7] J. Goodman, In: *Mechanics Applied to Engineering*, Longmans Green, London, 1899.
- [8] C. R. Soderberg, Factor of safety and working stress, *Transactions of the American Society of Mechanical Engineers*, **52**, 1939, pp. 13-28.
- [9] J. D. Morrow, *Fatigue Design Handbook*, Advances in Engineering, Vol. 4, Society of Automotive Engineers, Warrendale, PA, Sec. 3.2, pp. 21-29, 1968.
- [10] K. N. Smith, P. Watson and T. H. Topper, A stress-strain function for the fatigue of metals, *Journal of Materials*, **5**, 1970, pp. 767-778.

- [11] K. Walker, The effect of stress ratio during crack propagation and fatigue for 2024-T3 and 7075-T6 aluminum, *Effects of Environment and Complex Load History on Fatigue Life*, ASTM STP 462, American Society for Testing and Materials, West Conshohocken, Philadelphia, 1970, pp. 1-14.
- [12] N. E. Dowling, C. A. Calhoun and A. Arcari, Mean stress effects in stress-life fatigue and the Walker equation, *Fatigue and Fracture of Engineering Materials and Structures*, 32, 2009, pp. 163-179 (doi: 10.1111/j.1460-2695.2008.01322.x).